

NCCR 2021

**14th National Conference
for Clinical Research 2021**

"NICHE TO NORM"

**Conference
e-booklet**

NCCR 2021

18th - 20th AUGUST 2021

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Foreword

Former Minister of Health

YB Dato' Sri Dr. Adham Baba
Former Minister of Health, Malaysia

The Former Ministry of Health (MOH) prioritizes “Health for All”, and one way is by investing in clinical research that matters to the Malaysian people. Therefore, it is a privilege to be with clinicians to celebrate excellence in clinical research.

Malaysia strives for the conduct and translation of high-quality research by broadening human capital that is supported by a growing yet stable research ecosystem. Notably, the annual National Conference for Clinical Research (NCCR) serves as a gateway for researchers and clinicians worldwide to collaborate and share new ideas. I am therefore pleased that despite the challenges of COVID-19 pandemic, this year, the 14th NCCR will be held virtually to support researchers to present their findings.

The 14th NCCR 2021 features the theme “Niche to Norm”. In our COVID-19 time, we have witnessed the rapid development of COVID-19 vaccines, novel diagnostics, enhanced digital solutions, and adaptive clinical trials; all designed to help us recover from the pandemic. On that account, by highlighting these niche areas, the NCCR 2021 aspires to keep Malaysia abreast with the current progress in the global research scene. We look forward for this NCCR to enhance these niche areas.

On behalf of Former Ministry of Health, I would like to extend my appreciation and thanks to the Institute for Clinical Research, the Organizing Committee, the invited speakers, and to all those who contributed towards the success of this conference.

With that, I wish you all a great conference.

Foreword

Director General of Health

Tan Sri Dato' Seri Dr. Noor Hisham bin Abdullah
Director General of Health, Malaysia

I am delighted to be part of this year's 14th National Conference for Clinical Research (NCCR) themed, "Niche to Norm". This year's conference will address a triad of niche areas in medicine such as precision medicine, clinical research, and digital health. The update of the advances in these fields will sow the seed of reshaping and equipping the nation towards a sustainable future of health and healthcare.

The exponential growth in the global development of precision medicine in recent years is exhilarating, hence the 14th NCCR's focus on the niche is timely to provide the platform for us a glimpse through the future of healthcare. It is an exciting niche that will advance the sustainability of the healthcare system by maximizing the healthcare technologies in preserving the health of the nation. Therefore, the Malaysian healthcare industry will need to consider the myriads of issues such as the principle of ethics and legality, the cost and the value-added role, as well as the process of embedding data into workable action that has a meaningful impact on society.

Recently, Malaysia has attested to the world that we possess the quality in the clinical research that leads to the revolution of Hepatitis C's treatment and diagnosis. This historic clinical research breakthrough will reduce the overall cost and the duration of treatment of Hepatitis C desperately needed in the Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs). In addition, the introduction of a rapid diagnostic kit will project Malaysia onto the right path in the road of eliminating Hepatitis C by 2030 by tackling the disease at the point of care. This achievement should aspire the medical fraternity into the culture of clinical research in enhancing the nation's health.

With the continuous battle against the COVID-19 pandemic, the world has adopted digital approaches in healthcare to ensure effective and efficient service delivery. The acceptance of the MySejahtera solution in the public health strategies particularly in the digital contact tracing, vaccination program, and recently, home quarantine order as well as the normalization of outpatient clinical teleconsultations to reduce the risks of COVID-19 are propelling Malaysia towards achieving high digital adaptation in healthcare. We can seize the digital opportunities presented by the COVID-19 crisis to rethink and innovate our ways of delivering value-based healthcare for better patient outcomes.

I trust the conference will offer delegates the opportunity to exchange research ideas and share knowledge that can greatly benefit Malaysia as a leading destination for clinical research. On that note, I congratulate the Institute for Clinical Research and the Organizing Committee for gathering promising Malaysian researchers and renowned international speakers to the 14th NCCR.

I wish you all an enjoyable conference.

Foreword

Deputy Director General of Health

Datuk Dr. Hishamshah bin Mohd Ibrahim
Deputy Director General of Health, Malaysia
(Research and Technical Support)

The 14th National Conference for Clinical Research (NCCR) follows an annual tradition organized by the Institute for Clinical Research (ICR) NIH. This year, the NCCR spotlights the theme “Niche to Norm” which features precision medicine, clinical trials, and digital health.

Through the National Institutes of Health (NIH) the Ministry of Health Malaysia propels research ranging from clinical, biomedical, public health, health management, to health systems. As we chart individualized disease treatments with precision medicine, there is a need to advance digitalization in healthcare for both patient empowerment and facilitate clinical trials. With these special fields of interest in place, the NIH research ecosystem can keep pace with global research development, funding and support.

I look forward to the NCCR fostering professional development across diverse disciplines, widening research collaborations and developing new research in biomedical engineering. By working together, we can generate higher value and outcomes for policy and practice.

I would like to congratulate the Institute for Clinical Research and the Organizing Committee of 14th NCCR for their excellent scientific program. I also wish that the NCCR continues to galvanize the next generation of clinical researchers in Malaysia.

Foreword

Organizing Chairpersons

Dr. Kalaiarasu M. Peariasamy & Dr. Akhmal Yusof

Director of Institute for Clinical Research & CEO of Clinical Research Malaysia

The National Conference for Clinical Research (NCCR) is built on a strong heritage of clinical research dating back to our first NCCR in 2007. Despite the challenges of the pandemic, we have strived to bring virtual experiences that match the conventional way of conferencing.

Revolving around the theme “Niche to Norm,” the 14th NCCR 2021 features keynotes and plenaries in precision medicine, clinical trial, and digital health. Precision medicine is taking a foothold in patient management, especially in Malaysia with a diverse population such as ours. Additionally, the richness of existing biobanks in Malaysia can be a catalyst in furthering precision medicine research in the Southeast Asia region. By leveraging on strong collaborative efforts between researchers and clinicians from multiple disciplines, we are able to conduct clinical trials at a rate comparable with that of pre-pandemic years. The pandemic also provides unique research opportunities. For instance, in the field of digital health, the Institute for Clinical Research is undertaking research incorporating remote sensing biosensors and Artificial Intelligence for monitoring COVID-19 patients in quarantine.

It delights us that NCCR 2021 is continuing the tradition of the Dr. Wu Lien-Teh “Young Investigator Awards” to showcase and celebrate the efforts of our researchers. The Scientific Committee has worked hard to bring together internationally renowned speakers for plenary and symposiums, exhibitions and e-posters presentations from 179 accepted abstracts. We also would like to extend our utmost gratitude to all participants and sponsors for their invaluable support. On behalf of the Institute for Clinical Research and Clinical Research Malaysia, we are honored to welcome you to the 14th NCCR 2021. May you have an excellent and enjoyable conference.

Organizing Committees

Advisor

Datuk Dr. Hishamshah Mohd Ibrahim

Deputy Director General of Health (Research & Technical Support),
Ministry of Health, Malaysia

Chairperson

Dr. Kalaiarasu M. Peariasamy

Director, Institute for Clinical Research (ICR),
Ministry of Health, Malaysia

Co- Chairperson

Dr. Akhmal Yusof

CEO, Clinical Research Malaysia (CRM)

Scientific Committee Chairperson

Dr. Nor Fariza Ngah

Deputy Director, Institute for Clinical Research (ICR),
Ministry of Health, Malaysia

Secretary

Ms. Aida Basri

Mr. Zahid Hamidi

Ms. Naja Mohammad

CREST

Secretariat for Scientific Committee

Dr. Woon Yuan Liang (Lead)

Ms. Teh Hoon Shien (Lead)

Dr. Leong Chin Tho

Dr. June Lau Fei Wen

Ms. Yip Yan Yee

Institute for Clinical Research (ICR)

Organizing Committees

Scientific Reviewers

Dr. Nor Fariza Ngah (Lead)

Dr. Amy Hwong Wen Yea

Dr. Woon Yuan Liang

Dr. Loo Ching Ee

Dr. Wong Wen Jun

Dr. Kuan Pei Xuan

Dr. Ng Sock Wen

Ms. Lim Wei Yin

Ms. Yang Su Lan

Mr. Hing Yee Liang

Ms. Shridevi Subramaniam

Ms. Cheah Kit Yee

Institute for Clinical Research (ICR)

Poster & Presentation Judges

Prof. Dr. Sanjay Rampal Lekhraj Rampal

University of Malaya

Dr. Feisul Idzwan Mustapha

Disease Control Division, Ministry of Health, Malaysia

Dr. Cheah Wee Kooi

CRC Hospital Taiping

Coordinator

Dr. Norizan Rosli (Lead)

Dr. Sharifah Sarah Syed Mohamad Alwi

Ms. Syahirah Farhana Mohd Saleh

Institute for Clinical Research (ICR)

Master of Ceremony

Dr. Syarifah Nurul Ain Syed Badaruddin

CRC Hospital Sungai Buloh

Dr. Aimi Nadiah Jamel

Institute for Clinical Research (ICR)

Dr. Ooi Cheng Lee

Institute for Clinical Research (ICR)

Organizing Committees

Doa Reciter

Mr. Muhammad Zharul Nizam Bin Mutazah
Institute for Clinical Research (ICR)

Conference e-booklet

Dr. Aimi Nadiah Jamel
Dr. Ooi Cheng Lee
Dr. Nur Liana Md Nasir
Ms. Teh Hoon Shien
Ms. Nur Ain Zahidah Zainudin
Institute for Clinical Research (ICR)

Conference Registration & Payment

Mr. Law Wen Feng
Mrs. Farah Alicia Aeria
Ms. Leong Yien Yi
Ms. Chan Yinnfy
Infront Consulting Group APAC

Floor Manager

Dr. Nur Liana Md Nasir
Ms. Nurakmal Baharum
Ms. Nur Ain Zahidah Zainudin
Institute for Clinical Research (ICR)

Technical Support

Mrs. Hasnita Md Jaafar@Jaafar (Lead)
Mr. Ahmad Firdaus Zaidi
Mr. Alfian Zaidi Mohamad Yusof
Mr. Khusaini Mohd Daron
Mr. Mohamad Rizal Mohamad Rodzi
Mr. Mohd Azrانشah Hassan
Mr. Muhammad Dzulfadli Muhammad Ishak
Mr. Shariful Izwan Sharifudin
Mr. Sulaiman Harun
Mr. Zulqarnain Baharau
Mrs. Rafidah Hanem Md Dalil
Mrs. Zurriyati Yakub
Ms. Fadzlana A. Rahim
National Institutes of Health (NIH)

Organizing Committees

Secretariat for Organizing Committee

Dr. Siti Sabrina Kamarudin

Mr. Muhammad Zharul Nizam Mutazah

Mr. Muhamad Rasydan Zainal

Mrs. Nur Khairul Bariyyah Mohd Hatta

Mrs. Nur Khalisah Kaswan

Mrs. Rozila Harun

Mrs. Hazlinda Jamalludin

Ms. Airil Liyana Shakirah Yusof Khairan Nizar

Ms. Ainul Ashyikin Tan Ahmad Farid Tan

Ms. Khairul Nisa' Ishak

Ms. Anis Suraya Muhamad Nawawai

Ms. Roslina Husaini

Institute for Clinical Research (ICR)

Conference Programme

Day 1: 18th August 2021
Wednesday

0900 – 0930

Registration of Delegates

0930 – 0935

Welcome Speech

Dr Nor Fariza Ngah

Deputy Director, Institute for Clinical Research

0935 – 1000

Keynote Address

YBhg Tan Sri Dato' Seri Dr Noor Hisham Abdullah

Director General of Health, Ministry of Health, Malaysia

1000 – 1045

CRM Named Lecture

COVID-19 mRNA Vaccine Development

Professor Dr Kiat Ruxrungtham

Professor of Medicine, Department of Medicine
Chulalongkorn University & Scientific Chair of the
Chula Vaccine Research Centre

Moderator: Dr Akhmal Yusof

1045 – 1115

Keynote Lecture

**Clinical research aspects on COVID-19 variants
and booster dose**

Dr Anand Annamalai

Consultant Endocrinologist, Ashwin Specialty Hospital,
Vadamalayan Hospital

Moderator: Dr Kalaiarasu M. Peariasamy

1115 – 1145

Tea Break & Poster Viewing

Conference Programme

Day 1: 18th August 2021
Wednesday

1145 – 1300

Symposium 1: Precision Oncology - Translating Discovery to the Clinical Practice

Moderator: Amanda Lim Wei Yin

1150 – 1210

Genetics and Genomics of Breast Cancers in Asian Women

Professor Datin Paduka Dr Teo Soo Hwang
Chief Scientific Officer, Cancer Research Malaysia

1210 – 1230

Mining Large-scale Cancer Genome for Therapeutic and Predictive Biomarker Discovery

Professor Dr Leong Chee Onn
Deputy Director, Institute for Research, Development & Innovation, International Medical University

1230 – 1250

Polygenic Risk Score for Prediction of Breast Cancer in Asian Women

Associate Professor Dr Ho Weang Kee
Lecturer, School of Mathematical Sciences, University of Nottingham

1250 – 1300

Q&A

1300 – 1400

Lunch Break

Conference Programme

Day 1: 18th August 2021
Wednesday

1400 – 1535

Symposium 2: Precision Medicine in Diabetes Mellitus & Cardiovascular Health

Moderator: Audrey Lim Huili

1405 – 1425

Gender Differences in Drug Responses

Professor Dr Chim Choy Lang

Professor of Cardiology and Head of the Division of Molecular and Clinical Medicine, University of Dundee

1425 – 1445

Precision Medicine – PRIME Project

Dr Alexander Doney

Senior Lecturer and Honorary Consultant Physician, University of Dundee

1445 – 1505

Precision Medicine for Non-Communicable Diseases (NCD) Using the Genomics Approach

Professor Datuk Dr A. Rahman A. Jamal

Director, UKM Medical Molecular Biology Institute

1505 – 1525

Evidence on Cost-effectiveness of Precision Medicine for Cardiovascular Disease - Are they applicable to Malaysia?

Dr Lim Ka Keat

Research Fellow in Health Economics, King's College London

1525 – 1535

Q&A

1535 – 1600

Tea Break & Poster Viewing

Conference Programme

Day 1: 18th August 2021
Wednesday

1600 – 1630

Plenary 1:
**Lessons from COVID-19 for Linking Clinical
Research with Policy**

Vasee Moorthy, MD, PhD

Senior Advisor R&D, Research for Health Science
Division, World Health Organization

Moderator: Dr Loo Ching Ee

1630 – 1700

Plenary 2:
Phase 1 Clinical Trials Centre at HKU

Professor Dr Bernard Cheung Man Yung

Medical Director, Phase 1 Clinical Trials Centre,
University of Hong Kong

Moderator: Dr Loo Ching Ee

1700

Adjourn

Conference Programme

Day 2: 19th August 2021
Thursday

0830 – 0845

Registration of Delegates

0845 – 0915

ICR Named Lecture

Cohort/Biobank Studies towards Personal Prevention and Precision Medicine

Professor Sibrandes Poppema

President of Sunway University

Moderator: Dr Kalaiarasu M. Peariasamy

0915 – 1000

NCCR Opening Ceremony

- **Opening Address**

Dr Kalaiarasu M. Peariasamy

Director, Institute for Clinical Research

Dr Akhmal Yusof

CEO, Clinical Research Malaysia

- **Welcome Speech**

YBhg Datuk Dr Hishamshah Mohd Ibrahim

Deputy Director General of Health (P&ST) Ministry of Health, Malaysia

- **Officiating Speech, Launching of the 14th NCCR & NCCR Logo**

Tan Sri Dato' Seri Dr. Noor Hisham bin Abdullah

Director General of Health, Malaysia

Conference Programme

**Day 2: 19th August 2021
Thursday**

1000 – 1030

**Plenary 3:
Digital Health: Malaysia Original**

Professor Patrick Then Hang Hui

Professor & Head of School of ICT & Director of Centre for Digital Futures, Swinburne University of Technology Sarawak Campus

Moderator: Yang Su Lan

1030 – 1100

**Plenary 4:
Development of an AI-powered Mobile Phone Application for Early Detection of Oral Cancer**

Associate Professor Dr Chan Chee Seng

Associate Professor, Department of Artificial Intelligence, Faculty of Computer Science & Information Technology, Universiti Malaya

Moderator: Yang Su Lan

1100 – 1130

Tea Break & Poster Viewing

1130 – 1300

Dr Wu Lien-Teh Research Award Competition (Oral Presentation)

Oral Presentation Finalists:

1. **Dr Alia Daniella Abdul Halim**, Faculty of Medicine, UM/MOH
2. **Sivaraj A/L Raman**, Hospital Keningau
3. **Chan Huan Keat**, Hospital Sultanah Bahiyah
4. **Mahfuzah Ishak**, Hospital Sultan Nur Zahirah
5. **Fara Waheda Jusoh**, Hospital Sultanah Nur Zahirah

Emcee: Teh Hoon Shien

Conference Programme

Day 2: 19th August 2021
Thursday

1300 – 1400

Lunch Break

1400 – 1515

Symposium 3: Digital Health Research: From Engineering to Digital Health

Moderator: William Law Kian Boon

1405 – 1425

Are we ready to deploy artificial intelligence in clinical medicine?

Professor Dr Ng Kwan Hoong

Professor, Department of Biomedical Imaging,
Faculty of Medicine, Universiti Malaya

1425 – 1445

Emerging Technologies of Robotics in Healthcare

Prof Ir Ts Dr Ahmad `Athif Mohd Faudzi

Director, Centre for Artificial Intelligence and
Robotics, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia

1445 – 1505

Real World Evidence for Digital Health

Hassan Chaudhury

Global Digital Health Specialist, Healthcare United
Kingdom

1505 – 1515

Q&A

1515 – 1545

Tea Break & Poster Viewing

Conference Programme

**Day 2: 19th August 2021
Thursday**

1545 – 1615

**Plenary 5:
Diabetes Mellitus & Heart Failure: New Insights in
Translational Research**

Professor Dr Chim Choy Lang

Professor of Cardiology and Head of the Division of
Molecular and Clinical Medicine, University of Dundee

Moderator: Nicholas Hing Yee Liang

1615 – 1640

**Plenary 6:
Decentralize Clinical Trials to Unlock Value for
Patients**

Neha Sobti

Managing Director, Life Sciences, Accenture

Christina Gunther

Senior Manager, Life Sciences, European Clinical
Lead, Accenture

Moderator: Nicholas Hing Yee Liang

1640 – 1700

**Industry Talk 1:
Current Trends and Challenges in Healthcare
AI Research Publishing**

Ximena Alvira, MD, PhD

Clinical & Research Manager, Elsevier

Moderator: Nicholas Hing Yee Liang

1700

Adjourn

Conference Programme

Day 3: 20th August 2021
Friday

0800 – 0900

Registration of Delegates

0900 – 1015

**Symposium 4: COVID-19 Vaccine Trial:
Myth vs. Evidence**

Moderator: Chew Chun Keat

0905 – 0925

**Trials and tribulations in the covid era; An
overview of COVID19 vaccine trial in Malaysia**

Dr Yasmin Mohamed Gani

Infectious Disease Consultant, Hospital Sungai Buloh

0925 – 0945

**Preclinical research on the inactivated COVID-19
vaccine**

Professor Dr Shaozhong Dong

Deputy Director, Institute for Medical Biology, Chinese
Academy of Medical Sciences, China

0945 – 1005

**Key Points of Phase 1 study of SARS-CoV-2
(Inactivated) Vaccine**

Dr Qin Yu

Head of Phase 1 Clinical Research Unit, National Drug
Clinical Trial Institution of West China Second
University Hospital

1005 – 1015

Q&A

1015 – 1030

Tea Break & Poster Viewing

Conference Programme

**Day 3: 20th August 2021
Friday**

1030 – 1100

**Industry Talk 2:
Cloud Computing & Data Analytics in clinical
study: Our experience**

Dr Mohan Dass Pathmanathan

Research Medical Officer, Institute for Clinical
Research (MOH)

Law Wen Feng

Solutions Architect, Infront Consulting Group (M) Sdn
Bhd

Moderator: Dr Wong Wen Jun

1100 – 1215

**Symposium 5:
Research Advances in Traditional &
Alternative Medicine: Progressing to the
Future**

Moderator: Dr Norizan Rosli

1105 – 1125

**The Roadmap of T&CM Integration in Malaysian
Healthcare System towards Patient-centered Care**

Dr Jaspal Kaur Marik Singh

Senior Principal Assistant Director, Traditional and
Complementary Medicine Division, Ministry of Health
Malaysia

1125 – 1145

**Integrative Medicine for COVID-19: A Chimeric
Notion or A New Normal?**

Professor Dr Bhushan Patwardhan

Distinguished Professor, Center for Complementary
and Integrative Health, Interdisciplinary School of
Health Sciences, Savitribai Phule Pune University

Conference Programme

Day 3: 20th August 2021
Friday

1145 – 1205

Oncology Acupuncture: Precision Medicine & Patient Well-being

Dr Teo Chiah Sean

Head of T&CM Unit, National Cancer Institute, Ministry of Health Malaysia

1205 – 1215

Q&A

1215 – 1230

Dr Wu Lien-Teh Research Award Competition Prize Giving Ceremony

- **Speech by Dr Hor Chee Peng, Secretary General, Dr Wu Lien-Teh Society**
- **Dr Wu Lien-Teh Society video presentation**
- **Prize giving ceremony by Dr Kalaiarasu and Dr Hor Chee Peng**

1230 – 1245

Closing Ceremony

- **Closing Speech**

Dr Kalaiarasu M. Peariasamy

Director, Institute for Clinical Research

1245

Adjourn

Abstract List

Abstract List

Title and Authors

P-1

Characteristics of Inpatient Falls and Fall Related Injury

Bee Chiu Lim¹, Fatihah Mahmud¹, Bunyamin Abdullah², Muhammad Hazrul Badrul Hisham¹, Shanti Nalalingam³ & Fariz Safhan Mohamad Nor^{1,4}

1. Clinical Research Centre Hospital Tengku Ampuan Afzan, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Kuantan, Pahang
2. Quality Unit, Hospital Tengku Ampuan Afzan, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Kuantan, Pahang
3. Department of Nursing, Hospital Tengku Ampuan Afzan, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Kuantan, Pahang
4. Department of Nephrology, Hospital Tengku Ampuan Afzan, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Kuantan, Pahang

P-2

Asymptomatic COVID-19 Presentation in Children: Should We Screen?

Kuan Pei Xuan^{1,2}, Denisa Khoo³, Karisha Sivam³, Nurul Ain Naim⁴, Ong Li Teng⁴, See Kwee Ching⁴, Kalaiarasu M. Peariasamy^{3,5}

1. Digital Health Research and Innovation, Institute for Clinical Research, Malaysia
2. Clinical Research Centre, Sungai Buloh Hospital, Malaysia
3. Paediatric Dentistry Department, Sungai Buloh Hospital, Malaysia
4. Paediatric Department, Sungai Buloh Hospital, Malaysia
5. Director Office, Institute for Clinical Research, Malaysia

P-3

Methadone Substitution Therapy among Opioid Dependents: A Unicentric Experience

Khalid Karniza¹, Ooi Yit Tyse², Abdul Rashid Outbuddin², Mohammad Yusoff Muhammad Zul Azri², Jamaluddin Ruzita^{1,2}

1. Clinical Research Centre
2. Department of Psychiatry and Mental Health, Hospital Tuanku Fauziah, Perlis, Ministry of Health Malaysia

P-4

The Trend and Predictors for Tuberculosis Treatment Success Among Children in Malaysia Using MyTB Version 2.1 Database Over Five Years

S Maria Awaluddin^{1,2}, Nurhuda Ismail¹, Yuslina Zakaria³, Siti Munira Yasin¹, Asmah Razali⁴, Mohd Hatta Abdul Mutalip², Noor Aliza Lodz², Kamarul Imran Musa⁵, Faridah Kusin⁶, Tahir Aris⁷

1. Department of Public Health Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Sungai Buloh, Selangor
2. Institute for Public Health, National Institutes of Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia
3. Department of Pharmaceutical Life Sciences, Faculty of Pharmacy, University Teknologi MARA, Puncak Alam, Selangor, Malaysia
4. TB/Leprosy Sector, Disease Control Division, Ministry of Health, Malaysia
5. Department of Community Medicine, School of Medical Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia
6. Selangor Health State Department, Ministry of Health Malaysia
7. Institute for Medical Research, National Institutes of Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia

P-5

Cost-Effectiveness Analysis of a Combination Therapy Versus Monotherapy for Smoking Cessation

Tony Henderson Jeyarajah¹, Mohd Rizal Abdul Manaf¹

1. Kuala Lumpur Health Clinic, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia Medical Centre

P-6

Survival of patients with advanced and recurrent ovarian cancer treated using integrative medicine in Malaysia: A case series

Sharon Linus-Lojkip¹, Vijaendreh Subramaniam², Wei-Yin Lim³, Amar-Singh HSS¹

1. Clinical Research Centre (CRC), Hospital Raja Permaisuri Bainun, Ipoh, Perak, Ministry of Health, Malaysia
2. Dr Vijae Integrative Cancer Center, Mahkota Medical Center, Melaka, Malaysia
3. Centre for Clinical Epidemiology, Institute for Clinical Research, National Institutes of Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Selangor, Malaysia

P-7

Effect of Dialysis Modality on the Survival of End-Stage Renal Disease Patients Starting Dialysis in Sabah from 2007 to 2017: A Retrospective Cohort Study

Thamron Keowmani¹, Anis Kausar Ghazali², Najib Majdi Yaacob², Koh Wei Wong³

1. Clinical Research Centre, Hospital Queen Elizabeth, Kota Kinabalu, Sabah; 2. Unit of Biostatistics and Research Methodology, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Kubang Kerian, Kelantan; 3. Nephrology Unit, Hospital Queen Elizabeth, Kota Kinabalu, Sabah

P-8

The Impact of Living with Spinal Muscular Atrophy in Malaysia from Patients' and Caregivers' Perspectives

Karina Koh¹, Azlina Ahmad Annuar², Fahisham Taib³, Koh Cha Ling⁴, Edmund Lim Soon Chin⁵, Ch'ng Gaik Siew⁶

1. Clinical Research Centre, Hospital Kuala Lumpur, 2. Department of Biomedical Science, Faculty of Medicine, University of Malaya, 3. Department of Paediatrics, Hospital Universiti Sains Malaysia, 4. HELP University, Kuala Lumpur, 5. Persatuan Kebajikan Ceriajaya Kuala Lumpur Dan Selangor (WeCareJourney), 6. Genetics Department, Hospital Pulau Pinang.

Abstract List

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Title and Authors

P-9

Antibiotic Usage in the Early Phase of COVID-19 Pandemic: A National Perspective

Izzati-Nadhirah Mohamad¹, Calvin Ke-Wen Wong¹, Chii-Chii Chew², E-Li Leong², Biing-Horng Lee¹, Cheng-Keat Moh¹, Komalah Chenasammy¹, Chee-Loon Lim³, Hong-Bee Ker³
1. Medical Department, Hospital Raja Permaisuri Bainun (HRPB), Ipoh, Ministry of Health (MOH), Malaysia. 2. Clinical Research Centre, HRPB, Ipoh, MOH, Malaysia. 3. Infectious Diseases Unit, Medical Department, HRPB, Ipoh, MOH, Malaysia

P-10

Prevalence of Transfusion Transmitted Infection among Blood Donors in Perak State of Malaysia

Sabariah Mohd Noor¹, Tan Pei Pei¹, Jernih Abdul Rahman¹, Afifa Dzulkafli¹, Seetha Daywipragas¹, Thevasree Balakrishnan¹, Chang Chee Tao²
1. Transfusion Medicine Department, Hospital Raja Permaisuri Bainun 2. Clinical Research Centre, Hospital Raja Permaisuri Bainun

P-11

Satisfaction among Patients and Caregivers Receiving Value-Added Services during the Covid-19 Pandemic Outbreak in a Tertiary Hospital in the Perak State of Malaysia

Chew Lan Sim¹, Yeo Yee Ling¹, Chang Chee Tao², Chew Chii Chii², Doris George¹, Philip Rajan²
1. Pharmacy Department, Hospital Raja Permaisuri Bainun 2. Clinical Research Centre, Hospital Raja Permaisuri Bainun

P-12

Comorbidity And Its Impact on COVID-19 Positive Patients Who Died in Malaysia

Monica Danial^{1*}, Ann Lisa Arulappen², Shahrul Aiman Bin Soelar³, Alan Swee Hock Ch'ng^{1,4}, Irene Looi^{1,4}
1. Clinical Research Centre (CRC) Hospital Seberang Jaya, Institute for Clinical Research, Ministry of Health Malaysia (MOH); 2. Pharmacy Department Hospital Seberang Jaya, Institute for Clinical Research, Ministry of Health Malaysia (MOH); 3. Clinical Research Centre (CRC) Hospital Sultanah Bahiyah Hospital, Institute for Clinical Research, Ministry of Health Malaysia (MOH); 4. Medical Department, Hospital Seberang Jaya

P-13

Determinants of COVID-19 Vaccine Acceptance among Healthcare Workers in Penang

Gunenthira Rao¹, Anu Suria²
1. Public Health Medicine Specialist, Penang State Health Department 2. Medical Lecturer & Family Medicine Specialist, Universiti Sains Islam Malaysia

P-14

Paediatric Dosing Information in Package Insert of Antibiotics Used in a Malaysian Tertiary Hospital

Shamala Balan¹, Kirrthana Kanagarajah¹, Nor Anisa MD Salleh¹
1. Pharmacy Department, Hospital Tunku Azizah (HTA), Kuala Lumpur

P-15

Health Literacy among Adult Patients with Chronic Diseases in Sabah

Goh Qing Liang¹, Tan Sze Ling¹, Fong Pui Wun Fiona¹, Yen Chia How², Liao Siow Yen³
1. Department of Pharmacy, 2. Clinical Research Centre, Hospital Queen Elizabeth II, Kota Kinabalu, Sabah 3. Pharmacy Practice and Development Division, Sabah State Health Department, Kota Kinabalu, Sabah

P-16

Smartphone Addiction and Its Association With Depression, Anxiety and Stress: A Cross-Sectional Study Among Adults Attending Two Public Primary Care Clinics in Penang, Malaysia

Long SP^{1,6}, Lee M SY^{3,6}, Selaba M^{4,6}, Neogh KL^{2,6}, Ismail IA^{5,6}
1. Klinik Kesihatan Bukit Minyak, Kementerian Kesihatan Malaysia 2. Klinik Careist, 6, Lorong Seri Impian 1, 14000 Bukit Mertajam, Pulau Pinang 3. Klinik Lee, 29, Magazine Road, 10300 Penang 4. Klinik Kesihatan Seberang Jaya, Kementerian Kesihatan, Malaysia 5. Primary Care Medicine Department, Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) 6. Academy of Family Physicians of Malaysia (AFPM)

P-17

Awareness Of the Reflective Practice Implication Among Nurses of Public Hospital

Azlina DI, Sariah LI, Florence SI
1. Nursing Unit, Hospital Pakar Sultanah Fatimah

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1. Institute for Health Systems Research

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1. Biostatistics and Repository Data Sector, NIH Management Office, National Institute of Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Malaysia. 2. School of Medical Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia. 3. Hospital Universiti Sains Malaysia 4. Family Health Research Centre, Institute of Public Health, National Institute of Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Malaysia.

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1. Sector for Biostatistics & Data Repository, National Institutes of Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia 2. Institute for Public Health, National Institutes of Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia

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1. Institute for Medical Research, National Institutes of Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia 2. Biostatistics Centers & Data Repository, National Institutes of Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia 3. Kuala Lumpur Hospital, Ministry of Health Malaysia

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1. Clinical Research Center, Sarawak General Hospital. 2. Endocrinology Unit, Medical Department, Sarawak General Hospital

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1. Clinical Research Centre, Hospital Putrajaya

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1. Clinical Research Centre, Penang General Hospital 2. Medical Department, Penang General Hospital

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1. Department of Internal Medicine, International Islamic University, Kuantan, Pahang, Malaysia 2. Clinical Research Centre, Hospital Tengku Ampuan Afzan, Kuantan, Pahang, Ministry of Health 3. Kulliyah of Dentistry, International Islamic University, Kuantan, Pahang, Malaysia 4. Department of Medicine, University Malaya Medical Centre, Kuala Lumpur 5. Department of Medicine, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia Medical Centre 6. Pahang State Health Department, Kuantan, Ministry of Health

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1. Pharmacy Practice & Development Service Division (JKWPKL&P) 2. Hospital Putrajaya (HPJ) 3. District Cheras Health Office (JKWPKL&P) 4. Hospital Teluk Intan 5. Klinik Kesihatan Jinjang 6. Klinik Kesihatan Sungai Besi 7. Klinik Kesihatan Tanglin 8. Klinik Kesihatan Kuala Lumpur

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1. Internal Medicine Department, Hospital Tengku Ampuan Rahimah, Ministry of Health, Selangor, Malaysia 2. Internal Medicine Department, Hospital Teluk Intan, Ministry of Health, Perak, Malaysia. 3. Clinical Research Centre, Hospital Seri Manjung, Ministry of Health, Perak, Malaysia. 4. Internal Medicine Department, Hospital Seri Manjung, Ministry of Health, Perak, Malaysia. 5. Microbiology Department, Hospital Teluk Intan, Ministry of Health, Perak, Malaysia. 6. Microbiology Unit, Pathology Department, Hospital Seri Manjung, Ministry of Health, Perak, Malaysia

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1. Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, UCSI University, Jalan Menara Gading, UCSI Heights 56000 Cheras, Kuala Lumpur Malaysia 2. Faculty of Medicine, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Sungai Buloh Campus, Selangor Branch, 47000 Jalan Hospital, Sungai Buloh, Selangor, Malaysia 3. Brigham and Women's Hospital Endocrinology, Diabetes and Hypertension 221 Longwood Ave, Boston MA 4. Evidence Based Healthcare Sector, National Institute of Health (NIH), Persiaran Setia Murni, Setia Alam, 40170 Shah Alam, Selangor

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1. Clinical Research Centre, Hospital Taiping

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1. Sector for Biostatistics & Repository Data, NIH, MOH

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1. Centre of Clinical Epidemiology, Institute for Clinical Research, National Institutes of Health (NIH), 40170 Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia 2. Department of Radiotherapy and Oncology, Hospital Kuala Lumpur, Jalan Pahang, 50586 Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia 3. Breast & Endocrine Surgery Unit, Department of Surgery, Hospital Kuala Lumpur, 50586 Jalan Pahang Wilayah Persekutuan, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

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1. Department of Pharmacy, Hospital Sibul, Ministry of Health Malaysia

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1. Hospital Tunku Azizah , Kuala Lumpur 2. Section for Tuberculosis and Leprosy, Disease Control Division, Ministry of Health Malaysia.

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1. Digital Health Research Unit, Cancer Research Malaysia 2. Faculty of Dentistry, University of Malaya 3. Institute of Mathematical Sciences, University of Malaya, 4. Faculty of Computer Science and Information Technology, University of Malaya IRB: Faculty of Dentistry Medical Ethics Committee, University of Malaya

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1. Clinical Research Centre, Sibul Hospital, Sarawak, Malaysia 2. Faculty of Medicine, SEGi University Sibul Clinical Campus, Sarawak, Malaysia

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1. Hospital Kajang

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1. Clinical Research Centre, Sarawak General Hospital, Sarawak, Malaysia

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Norili Farhana Ahmad Saber¹, Asrenee Ab Razak², Suria Hussin¹
1. Department of Psychiatry, Hospital Raja Perempuan Zainab II, Kota Bharu, Kelantan 2. Department of Psychiatry, Hospital Universiti Sains Malaysia, Kubang Kerian, Kelantan

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1. Department of Psychiatry, School of Medical Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia. 2. Department of Chemical Pathology, School of Medical Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia. 3. Unit of Biostatistics and Research Methodology, School of Medical Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia 4. Hospital Universiti Sains Malaysia, 16150 Kubang Kerian, Kelantan.

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1. Digital Health Research and Innovation (DHRi), Institute for Clinical Research 2. Director Office, Institute for Clinical Research

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1. Hospital Melaka, Ministry of Health

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1. MB Healthcare Academy 2. Clinical Research Centre, Hospital Sultan Ismail, Johor Bahru Malaysia 3. Clinical School Johor Bahru, Jeffrey Cheah School of Medicine and Health Sciences, Monash University Malaysia, Johor Bahru, Malaysia 4. Kempas Medical Centre

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1. Pejabat Kesihatan Daerah Alor Gajah, Melaka

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1. Pharmacy Department HSNZ, Kuala Terengganu, Terengganu 2. Unit of Biostatistics & Research Methodology, School of Medical Sciences, USM Health Campus, Kelantan 3. Clinical Research Centre HSNZ, Kuala Terengganu, Terengganu 4. Neurology Department HSNZ, Kuala Terengganu, Terengganu

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1. Digital Health Research & Innovation (DHRi) Unit, Institute for Clinical Research, NIH. 2. Director Office, Institute for Clinical Research, NIH

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Lim Ming Yao¹, Lem Fui Fui¹
1. Clinical Research Centre, Queen Elizabeth Hospital

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Nadiah Sa'at¹, Anis Kausar Ghazali¹, Najib Majdi Yaacob¹, Mohamad Aziz Salowi²
1. Universiti Sains Malaysia, USM; 2. Hospital Selayang, Selangor, Malaysia

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Farahdila H1, Anita A1, Zamtira S1, Rozita MY1, Azahadi O1
1. Sector for Biostatistics & Repository Data, NIH, MOH

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1. Pharmacy Department HSNZ, Kuala Terengganu, Terengganu 2. Clinical Research Centre HSNZ, Kuala Terengganu, Terengganu 3. Neurology Department HSNZ, Kuala Terengganu, Terengganu 4. Emergency Department HSNZ, Kuala Terengganu, Terengganu

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1. Pejabat Kesihatan Daerah Temerloh, Pahang

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Lee Jeffrey Soon Yit1, Lo Chai Lian2, Lim Rainie2, Thanasegaran Srivithiya2, Wong April Ling Siew2, Toh Teck Hock1
1. Clinical Research Centre, Sibu Hospital, Sibu, Sarawak 2. Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Sibu Hospital, Sibu, Sarawak.

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Calyn Tan Jen Ai1, Mohd Kamarulariffin Kamarudin2
1. Health Performance Unit, Sector for Evidence Based Healthcare, Office of NIH Manager, National Institutes of Health (NIH), Ministry of Health Malaysia 2. Department of Social and Preventive Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, University of Malaya, 50603, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

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1. Clinical Research Centre, Sibu Hospital, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Sibu, Sarawak, Malaysia. 2. Department of Paediatrics, Sibu Hospital, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Sarawak, Malaysia. 3. Faculty of Medicine, SEGi University, Kota Damansara, Selangor, Malaysia. 4. Department of Paediatrics, Bintulu Hospital, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Bintulu, Sarawak, Malaysia. 5. Department of Medicine, Sibu Hospital, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Sibu, Sarawak, Malaysia. 6. Sibu Divisional Health Office, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Sarawak, Malaysia

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NurAmira Zulkifli1, Tan Mei See1, Teng Wei1
1. Hospital Kepala Batas, Pulau Pinang, Malaysia

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Julian Valerie John Jembail1, Charlene Wong Yi Lin1, Nur Alia Muhammad Amir Bakhtiar1, Siti Nursuraya Md Lazim1, Kuan Pei Xuan2, Chua Pin Fen1
1. Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, University Malaysia Sarawak, Malaysia, 2. Digital Health Research and Innovation, Institute for Clinical Research, Malaysia

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1. Pharmacy Department, Sultanah Nur Zahirah Hospital, Terengganu, Malaysia

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Sim Shin Mei1, Emily Chung Shin Ni1, Wong Sui Fern1, Shirlie Chai1,2, Kamarudin Ahmad1,2
1. Pharmacy Department, Miri Hospital, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Sarawak 2. Clinical Research Centre Miri, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Sarawak

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Yong Sook-Min¹, Lee Jeffrey Soon-Yit¹, Toh Teck-Hock¹
1. Clinical Research Centre, Sibul Hospital, Sibul, Sarawak

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Richard Lim¹, Yeat Choi Ling², Nirmala Kasinathan², Siti Zubaidah Ahmad Subki³, Arvinder Singh H. S.4, Nur Dalila Binti Saad²
1. Palliative Unit, Selayang Hospital 2. Palliative Unit, Raja Permaisuri Bainun Hospital, Ipoh 3. Medical Development Unit, Ministry of Health Malaysia 4. National Institute Of Health, Setia Alam

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1. Universiti Sains Malaysia 2. Hospital Keningau, MOH 3. Hospital Tengku Ampuan Rahimah, MOH 4. Hospital Umum Sarawak, MOH 5. Samarahan Divisional Dental Office, MOH 6. Digital Health Research Unit, Cancer Research Malaysia 7. University of Malaya

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1. Sibul Hospital, Sarawak

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1. Hospital Tunku Azizah, Kuala Lumpur 2. UiTM Selayang Campus, Kuala Lumpur 3. Faculty of Medicine, University of Malaya 4. Hospital Melaka 5. Hospital Pakar Sultanah Fatimah, Muar 6. Hospital Sultanah Nora Ismail, Batu Pahat 7. Hospital Segamat 8. Hospital Enche' Besar Hajjah Kalthom, Kluang 9. Hospital Duchess of Kent, Sandakan 10. Hospital Sultanah Aminah, Johor Bahru 11. Hospital Wanita dan Kanak kanak, Likas, Kota Kinabalu 12. Hospital Sultan Ismail, Johor Bahru.

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1. Hospital Pakar Sultanah Fatimah

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1. Pejabat Kesihatan Daerah Rembau

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1. Department of Paediatric, Hospital Tunku Azizah, Kuala Lumpur 2. Hospital Selayang 3. Hospital Sultanah Nur Zaherah 4. Hospital Kajang 5. Hospital Kuala Krai 6. Hospital Tengku Ampuan Afzan 7. Hospital Sultan Abdul Halim 8. Hospital Seberang Jaya, 9. Hospital Sultanah Bahiyah 10. Hospital Tuanku Fauziah 11. Hospital Tuanku Jaafar Seremban 12. Hospital Port Dickson 13. Hospital Melaka 14. Hospital Pakar Sultanah Fatimah 15. Hospital Segamat 16. Hospital Sultanah Nora Ismail 17. Hospital Sultanah Aminah 18. Hospital Sultan Ismail 19. Hospital Seri Manjung, 20. Hospital Taiping 21. Hospital Raja Permaisuri Bainun, 22. Hospital Umum Sarawak, 23. Hospital Sibul 24. Hospital Bintulu.

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Arvinder Singh HS1

1. PhD Candidate at Community Health Department, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia 2. Institute of Clinical Research Malaysia, Ministry of Health Malaysia

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Alia Daniella AH, MD, MPH1,2, Awang Bulgiba, MPH, PhD2

1. Ministry of Health Malaysia 2. University of Malaya

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1. Transfusion Medicine Department, Hospital Raja Permaisuri Bainun Ipoh, Perak 2. Clinical Research Centre, Hospital Raja Permaisuri Bainun Ipoh, Perak

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1. Pathology Department, Sungai Buloh Hospital, 47000 Sungai Buloh, Selangor, Malaysia.

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1. Nursing Unit, Hospital Pakar Sultanah Fatimah

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1. Department of Ophthalmology, Hospital Tuanku Fauziah , Kangar , Perlis.

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1. Department of Pharmacy, Sungai Buloh Hospital, Ministry of Health Malaysia

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1. Digital Health Research and Innovation, Institute for Clinical Research, Malaysia 2. Director Office, Institute for Clinical Research, Malaysia

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1. Seberang Jaya Hospital 2. Kepala Batas Hospital

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Narwani Hussin1, Awisul-Islah Ghazali1, Ramli Ibrahim2, Masnor Mat Daud3, Sukri Ahmad4

1. Hospital Taiping, Perak 2. Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, UCSI University, Terengganu 3. Hospital Tengku Anis, Pasir Puteh, Kelantan 4. Hospital Raja Perempuan Zainab II, Kota Bharu, Kelantan

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Loo Ching Ee¹, Woon Yuan Liang¹, Leong Chin Tho¹, Ahmad Bustamam Ros Suzanna², Hj Abdul Wahab Mohamed Yusof³, Mohd Hashim Siti Sabzah⁴, R Jeganathan J Ravichandran⁵, Hing Yee Liang¹, Lau June Fei Wen¹, Lian Fiona Suling¹, Lim Wei Yin¹, Subramaniam Kalianan Ramanil, Subramaniam Shridevi¹, Teh Hoon Shien¹, Wong Wen Jun¹, Mustapha Feisul⁶, Teo Soo Hwang⁷ And The Dedicate Study Group
1. Centre for Clinical Epidemiology, Institute for Clinical Research, National Institutes of Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Selangor, Malaysia 2. Department of Radiotherapy and Oncology, Kuala Lumpur Hospital, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia 3. Department of Surgery, Tengku Ampuan Rahimah Hospital, Selangor, Malaysia 4. Department of Otolaryngology, Hospital Sultanah Bahiyah Kedah, Malaysia 5. Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Sultanah Aminah Hospital, Johor, Malaysia 6. Disease Control Division, Ministry of Health, Putrajaya, Malaysia 7. Cancer Research Malaysia, Selangor, Malaysia

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1. Centre for Clinical Epidemiology, Institute of Clinical Research, National Institute of Health, 2. Institute for Health Behavioural Research, National Institute of Health, 3. Health Economics Research Centre, Nuffield Department of Population Health, University of Oxford, Oxford, UK

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Yip Yan Yee¹, Chew Cheng Hoon¹, Kalaiarasu M. Peariasamy¹
1. Institute for Clinical Research, Ministry of Health, Malaysia

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Anita A¹, Farahdila H¹, Rozita MY¹, Azahadi O¹
1. Sector for Biostatistics & Repository Data, NIH, MOH

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1. Institute for Medical Research, National Institute of Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Jalan Pahang, 50588, Kuala Lumpur. 2. Sector for Biostatistics and Data Repository, National Institutes of Health, Ministry of Health Malaysia, 40170, Shah Alam, Selangor. 3. Hospital Putlan Ismail, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Taman Mount Austin, 81100, Johor Bahru, Johor. 4. Hospital Putrajaya, Ministry of Health Malaysia, Presint 7, 62250 Putrajaya, Wilayah Persekutuan Putrajaya

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1. Sector for Biostatistics & Data Repository, NIH 2. Institute for Public Health, NIH

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Lai Pei Kuan¹, Sivalingam Nalliah¹, Teng Cheong Lieng¹, Nicole Chen Lee Ping¹
1. International Medical University (IMU)

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Wong Vei Seng^{1, 2}, Amalina Anuar³, Leong Jie Xiang², Syed Addi Usmi Syed Othman²
1. Department of Orthopaedics, Hospital Pengajar Universiti Putra Malaysia, Selangor, Ministry of Health Malaysia 2. Department of Orthopaedics, Hospital Tuanku Fauziah, Perlis, Ministry of Health Malaysia 3. Clinical Research Centre (CRC), Hospital Tuanku Fauziah, Kangar, Perlis, Ministry of Health Malaysia

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Shanta Sathia Moorthy^{1, 2}, Balamurugan Tangiisuran^{2,3}, Parthiban Sivasamy⁴
1. Pharmacy Department, Hospital Pakar Sultanah Fatimah, Muar, Johor 2. School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia 3. National Poison Centre, Universiti Sains Malaysia 4. School of Medicine, KPJ Healthcare University College

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Tee Khim Boon¹, Luqman Ibrahim¹, Najihah Mohd Hashim¹, Mohd Zuwairi Saiman¹, Zaril Harza Zakaria², Hasniza Zaman Huri¹
1. Universiti Malaya 2. National Pharmaceutical Regulatory Agency

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Mohemmad Rizal Mohemmad Redzuan^{1, 2}, Khan Amer Hayat¹, Harun Sabariah Noor¹, Saleh Zaiton²
1. Department of Clinical Pharmacy, School of Pharmaceutical Science, University Science Malaysia 2. Lembah Pantai Health Office, Ministry of Health Malaysia

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Diana Muhd Rizal¹, Jeeshalini Rajadurai¹, Ying Xin Lai¹, Nur Amalina Hamdan¹, Ismyth Abdrahman²
1. Department of Pharmacy, Port Dickson Hospital, Negeri Sembilan, Ministry of Health Malaysia 2. Department of Orthopedic, Port Dickson Hospital, Negeri Sembilan, Ministry of Health Malaysia

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Ms. Yap Ai Ching¹, Mr. Mohemmad Rizal Mohemmad Redzuan¹, Mr. Segeran Sugendiren¹
1. Klinik Kesihatan Tanglin

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1. Department of Emergency and Trauma, Bukit Mertajam Hospital, Ministry of Health Malaysia. 2. Department of Management, Seberang Jaya Hospital. 3. The Royal College of Emergency Medicine, UK

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1. Pharmacy Department, Sibul Hospital, 2. Klinik Kesihatan Bintulu, 3. Pejabat Farmasi Bahagian Sibul, 4. Klinik Kesihatan Selangau

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Ahmad Zaid ZANIALI, Subapriya SUPPIAH², Siti Zarina AMIR HASSANI
1. Department of Nuclear Medicine, Hospital Kuala Lumpur 2. Department of Imaging, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Universiti Putra Malaysia

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Siti Sabrina Kamarudin¹, Nurizati binti Mat Ghani¹, Rabihtul Adawiyah binti Egar¹, Nor Azizah binti Mohamad Nazri¹, Nor Fariza binti Ngah¹
1. Clinical Research Centre, Hospital Shah Alam²

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Ismat Mohd Sulaiman¹, Awang Bulgiba², Sameem Abdul Kareem³
1. Planning Division, Ministry of Health Malaysia 2. Faculty of Medicine, University of Malaya 3. Faculty of Computer Science & Information Technology

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Saharudin Siti Nurhafizah¹, Ngah Nor Fariza¹, Kunchi Raman Renuga², Fadzil Siti Sarah², Omar Nur Farha², Othman Ruzita³
1. CRC, 2. UKA, 3. Hospital Director, Hospital Shah Alam, Selangor.

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YW Tan¹, KP Tiang¹, I.M Muzakkir¹, Tharanitharan R¹, YL Quek¹
1. Department of General Surgery, Hospital Sungai Buloh

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Asbi Atiqah¹, Tong Seng Fah¹, Sulaiman Nadirah²
1. Pusat Perubatan Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia 2. Hospital Queen Elizabeth

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1. Nursing Unit, Hospital Pakar Sultanah Muar Johor

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SH Lim¹, TL Tan¹, PW Ngo¹, LY Lee¹, SY Ting², HJ Tan³
1. Medical Department, Hospital Seri Manjung, Perak, Ministry of Health, Malaysia 2. Clinical Research Department, Hospital Seri Manjung, Perak, Ministry of Health, Malaysia 3. Neurology Department, Hospital Kuala Lumpur, Kuala Lumpur, Ministry of Health, Malaysia

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1. Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Head & Neck Surgery, Hospital Sungai Buloh, Selangor, Malaysia

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KP Tiang¹, RAHMAN Mokhtar¹, MUZAKKHIR Ibrahim¹, YL Quek¹, RAZALI IBRAHIMI
1. Department of Surgery, Hospital Sungai Buloh

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Krishinan Sotheenathan¹, Abdul Kareem Basheer Ahamad¹, Subramaniam Suganthi Rani¹, Sivasangari Subramaniam^{1,2}
1. Department of Cardiothoracic Surgery Hospital Pulau Pinang 2. Clinical Research Centre Hospital Pulau Pinang

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Chin Hui Ng¹, Hoey Lin Oh¹, Calvin Ke Wen Wong², Biing Horng Lee³, Kah Shuen Thong¹, Kit Weng Foong⁴
1. Pharmacy Department, Raja Permaisuri Bainun Hospital, 30400 Ipoh, Perak, Malaysia 2. Medical Department, Sarawak General Hospital, 93586 Kuching, Sarawak, Malaysia 3. Medical Department, Taiping Hospital, Perak, 34000 Malaysia 4. Anesthesiology Department, Raja Permaisuri Bainun Hospital, 30400 Ipoh, Perak, Malaysia

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1. Clinical Research Center, Cardiology Department, QEHI

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1. Nursing Unit, Hospital Pakar Sultanah Fatimah Muar, Johor

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1. Department of Oncology Pharmacy, Hospital Seri Manjung, Perak, Malaysia. 2. Department of Surgery, Hospital Seri Manjung, Perak, Malaysia.

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Wan Nadiah AH1, Hor SM2
1. Department of Ophthalmology, Tuanku Fauziah Hospital 2. Department of Ophthalmology, Kulim Hospital

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Ch'ng Wan Ping¹, Mohammad Firdaus Bin Abdul Aziz²
1. Master of Health Research Ethics (MOHRE), Faculty of Medicine, University of Malaya. 2. Faculty of Law, University of Malaya.

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1. ENT Department Hospital Shah Alam, Malaysia

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Nur Khadijah Muhamad Jamil^{1,2}, Nurul Asma Abdullah², Ruzilawati Abu Bakar², Imran Ahmad²
1. Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin 2. Universiti Sains Malaysia

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